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ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
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“OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB MASALASI: TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS”

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OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB MASALASI: TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS

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OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB

MASALASI: TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS

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To'plamdan medialingvistikaning dolzarb masalalari, mediamatnlarning ta'sirchanligini oshirish yo'llari, noshirlik sohasini rivojlantirishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlariga oid yangiliklar, adabiyotshunoslik masalalari, tarjima mahorati, innovatsion g'oyalar va texnologiyalar, o'zbek tilining sohada qo'llanilishi, OAV matnlarining tili, uslubi va tahriri sohasida mavjud muammolarga bag'ishlangan maqolalar o'rin olgan. Undan mazkur sohada ilmiy tadqiqot olib borayotgan olimlar, tadqiqotchilar, magistrant va talabalar foydalanishi mumkin, shuningdek, ommaviy axborot vositalarida til va uslub muammolarining yechimini izlash, tahlil, tasnif va qiyos asosida tegishli xulosalar chiqarish va tavsiyalar berishda ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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Buranova Barno Menglibayevna

filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Nazarova Munira Yusupovna

O'zJOKU PhD tadqiqotchi

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ART-JURNALISTIKADA IXTISOSLASHUV MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada jurnalistika sohasidagi ixtisoslashuv, xususan san'at va uning turlarini yorituvchi, tahlil qiluvchi mutaxassislar, art-jurnalistlarning shakllanish bosqichlari, bu jarayonda san'atkorlarning o'rni haqida so'z boradi. Bugun sohada faoliyat olib borayotgan art-jurnalistlar faoliyati qisman tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, art-jurnalist faoliyati qaysi vazifalarni qamrab olishiga aniqlik kiritilib, uning funksiyalari klassifikatsiya qilingan. Sohada ixtisoslashgan jurnalistlar yetishib chiqishida san'atning muayyan turlariga bag'ishlangan davriy nashrlar ta'siri o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: art-jurnalist, tanqidchilik, madaniyat, badiiy did, ixtisoslashuv.

Kirish

San'at – insoniyat tamaddunining ajralmas qismi. Art-jurnalistika mazkur sohada axborotni tarqatish, tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish, badiiy didni shakllantirish, doimiy o'sib boruvchi ijod jarayonlarini hujjatlashtirish uchun muhim vosita sifatida media maydonidan o'rin oldi.

Milliy matbuotda jadidlar boshlab bergan san'at mavzularini yoritish sho'rolar davrida san'atning barcha turlarini qamrab oluvchi davriy nashrlar, maxsus tele-, radio loyihalarning yo'lga qo'yilishi orqali davom etdi. Mazkur tizimda san'at sohasini yoritish uchun jurnalistikaning barcha an'anaviy janrlari rivojlandi, asosiy e'tibor tahliliy mazmunga ega bo'lgan maqolalarga yo'naltirildi. Jurnalistlar bilan san'atshunoslar, san'atkorlar ham hamkorlik qildi. Jumladan, "Qizil O'zbekiston" gazetasining o'zida mashhur rus bastakori hamda direjyori R.M.Glierning "Gulsara" muzikasi haqida" (1937-yil 23-aprel), taniqli bastakor va sozanda To'xtasin Jalilovning "O'zbek muzikasining yangi qonuni" (1937-yil 28-aprel), SSSR xalq artistlari Muxtor Ashrafiy hamda Muhiddin Qori Yoqubovlar (o'zbek operasi haqida "Birinchi qadamlarning saboqlari" (1935-yil 14-oktyabr), o'zbek musiqasi haqida "Kasalliklarimizning siri" (1935-yil 21-sentyabr), "O'zbek sovet operasini yaratamiz" (1938-yil, 28-avgust), xalq artistlari Halima Nosirova "San'atimiz haqida ba'zi bir fikrlar" (1938-yil, 24-mart), Sora Eshonto'rayeva O'zbek davlat akademik drama teatri to'g'risida "Teatrimiz xalq xizmatida" (1939-yil 5-sentyabr), Abror Hidoyatov "Boy ila xizmatchi" dramasi haqida sahnaga qo'yilish munosabati bilan "Faxrlanaman" (1939-yil 27-may), Shukur Burhon matbuot kuni munosabati bilan "Qizil O'zbekiston" gazetasi haqida "Sevgan gazetam" (1940-yil, 5-may) singari atoqli san'atkorlarning chiqishlari jurnalistikaning yana bir ixtisoslashgan tarmog'i shakllanishiga hissa qo'shdi. Art-jurnalistika asta-sekin matbuotda professional bahs va munozaralarga boy materiallar bilan birgalikda san'atning tarixiy shakllari hamda zamonaviy holati bilan bog'liq muammolarni yorituvchi platformaga aylandi.

Natija va mulohazalar

San'at tanqidchiligi jurnalistikaning bir yo'nalishi sifatida san'at hodisalariga ham estetik, ham ijtimoiy ahamiyati jihatidan baho beradi. Binobarin, musiqa, teatr, tasviriy san'at tanqidchiligining o'zi muayyan davr badiiy qarashlari, hukmron did hamda san'at tarixini o'zida aks ettiradi. U nafaqat real, balki ideal mazmunga ega

bo'lib, bu esa publitsistdan san'atkor bilan birgalikda ijod qilish va dunyoni san'atkor kabi badiiy idrok etishni talab qiladi. "San'atning haqiqiy ijodkorlari: bastakorlar, rassomlar, aktyorlar, rejissyorlar shu tarzda matbuotda namoyon bo'ladi. Bu rus tanqidchiligidagi muhim lahza, chunki buning natijasida ijtimoiy-madaniy makon kengaydi, o'quvchilar doirasi o'sdi. Can'at asarlari yaratuvchilarining fikri, sohadagi muammolarni "ichkari"dan ko'rish har doim qiziq bo'lgan. Ayniqsa, V.G.Belinskiy davridan buyon nafaqat adabiy, balki san'at tanqidchiligi ham uzoq vaqt o'zining publitsistik xususiyatini saqlab kelayotgan edi. Biroq, estetik hamda ijtimoiy munosabatini yanada aniqroq belgilashi, asarining badiiy g'oyasini soddaroq ifodalay olish uchun san'atkorning matbuotdagi faoliyati ham muhim edi"¹.

Tadqiqotchi G.S.Lapshina tahliliga ko'ra, san'at jurnalistikasining alohida ixtisoslashgan yo'nalish sifatida shakllanib chiqishida faqatgina san'at havasmandlari, qiziquvchilarigina emas, balki san'atkorlarning o'zlari ham baholi qudrat hissa qo'shdilar. Ularning matbuot orqali chiqishlari nafaqat o'quvchilar, balki asarning izohi, muallif ifodasi, yondashuvini, ijtimoiy ahamiyatini "tushuntirish" uchun qulay maydonga aylandi. Bu esa o'z navbatida sohaga qiziquvchi alohida auditoriya bilan birga san'atga ixtisoslashgan mualliflar jamoasining shakllanishiga turtki bo'ldi.

Ommaviy axborot vositalari jamoatchilik fikrini shakllantirishda katta rol o'ynaydi. Shu bois art-jurnalistning vazifasi san'at sohasidagi yangiliklar, tendensiyalarni o'quvchiga yetkazish bilan cheklanmaydi. U odamlarga muayyan madaniy qadriyatlar haqida o'z fikrini shakllantirish, jamoatchilik e'tiborini ma'naviy rivojlanishning ahamiyatiga qaratishga yordam beradi.

Zamonaviy san'at tez-tez yangiliklar, o'zgarishlarga uchraydi. Shunga qaramay, san'at jamiyat hayotida o'z ahamiyatini hech qachon yo'qotmagan. Undagi o'ziga xoslik – hech qanday qoidalarga ega emasligi, ijoddagi erkinlik va ijodkorning o'zini

¹ Г.С.Гапшина. Искусства глазами журналиста. М.: 2015., стр.7 (346 бет)

namoyon qilish istagida jamlanadi. San'atni yoritayotgan jurnalistdan bu sohani ichidan yaxshi bilishi, auditoriya ehtiyoji, mumtoz san'at namunalari bilan birga ayni vaqtdagi bugungi tendensiyalardan boxabar bo'lish talab qilinadi. Auditoriya bilan ijodkor o'rtasida masofa yuzaga kelmasligi uchun ana shu nozik o'rtalikni ushlab lozim. Yuksak badiiylik qiymatini, mumtoz asarlarni chuqur his qila olgan mutaxassis har doim ham yangi oqimlar, trendlarni oson qabul qilishga tayyor bo'lavermaydi. Shu bois art-jurnalist bir vaqtning o'zida keng omma bilan birga san'at sohasi mutaxassislari uchun ham yoza olishi joiz. Uning yozganlari faqatgina subyektiv qarashlarga tayanilmay, soha mutaxassislari va asarning tarixiy qiymati bilan ham asoslanadi.

Bosma nashrlari ichida san'at sport jurnalistikasidan so'ng ixtisoslashgan katta va murakkab yo'nalishlardan sanaladi. Bu yo'nalishda ijod qilayotgan jurnalist san'at va uning tarixini bilishi, chuqur his etishi, tushunishi, keng auditoriya savollariga javob bera olishi lozim. San'at – serqirra soha. Art-jurnalistika ixtisoslashuvining ichida ham tor ixtisosliklar: musiqa, teatr, kino, tasviriy san'at jurnalistikasiga ixtisoslashgan mutaxassislar faoliyat olib boradi. San'atshunoslardan farqli ravishda ular san'at qonuniyatlarini emas, balki uning jamiyat hayotiga ta'sirini o'rganadi.

Milliy jurnalistika, xususan matbuotda san'at mavzularini yoritishga ixtisoslashish – art jurnalistikaning shakllanish jarayonlari bevosita teatr, kino, rangtasvir san'ati va sanoatidagi muhim o'zgarishlar bilan hamohang ravishda o'sib, o'zgarib bordi. Davriy bosma nashrlar faoliyatining dastlabki namunalari dayoq madaniyat va san'at mavzusiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan bo'lsa, keyinroq san'at asarlari, mahalliy teatr hamda kino san'ati haqida tushuncha berishga bag'ishlangan bir nechta davriy bosma nashrlar faoliyati yo'lga qo'yildi.

Art-jurnalistika sohadagi nisbatan yangi, zamonaviy yo'nalish bo'lib, uning an'anaviy jurnalistikadan farqi faqatgina san'at va madaniyatga doir xabar va yangiliklarni berish bilan cheklanmay, balki san'at asarlarining interpretatsiyasi

(talqini) va tahliliga ham e'tibor qaratadi. Butun dunyoda jurnalistikaning mazkur yo'nalish rivojlanib, uning media makonga ta'siri tobora ortib bormoqda. Mamlakat madaniy hayotida san'atga ixtisoslashgan davriy nashrlarning ahamiyati katta.

San'atni "so'zsiz muloqot" deb bejiz aytishmaydi. Nashrlar havaskorlar bilan bir qatorda san'at va madaniyat mutaxassislari, tanqidchi san'atshunoslarga fikr almashish uchun yaxshi bir maydon vazifasini ham o'taydi. Qolaversa asarlarni kattaroq masshtabda tarqalishi, keng auditoriy e'tiboriga tushish uchun matbuot muhim vositachi vazifasini bajaradi.

Bugungi media imkoniyatlari, axborot olish usullari shiddat bilan rivojlanayotgan davr – XXI asrda madaniy hayotni elektron media vositalarisiz tasavvur qilish qiyin. Internet tarmoqlari orqali san'at sohasidagi ko'plab hodisalar, yangiliklar to'g'ridan-to'g'ri auditoriya e'tiboriga havola qilinadi. Hatto san'atkorlarning o'zida ham o'z faoliyati, ijodi, o'zi bilan tanishtirish imkoniyati bor. Shunga qaramay, hanuz XIX-XX asrning mumtoz jurnalistikasi janrlariga talab mavjud. San'at olamida bo'layotgan har qanday jarayonlar aynan mumtoz jurnalistika janrlari orqali tahlil va tanqidga tortilmoqda. Bu orqali ular faqatgina nashrning yashab qolishini emas, balki mamlakat madaniy hayotiga ma'lum ma'noda ta'sir etib, voqelikka munosabat shakllanishiga xissa qo'shadi. Art-jurnalistika ommaviy axborot vositalarining paradoksal sohasidir. Uning obyekti hech qachon o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmaydi, chunki madaniy hayotga doir xabarlar hamisha talabgir. Qolaversa, axborot – eng tez eskiruvchi "tovar" (mahsulot) deb topilgan bir paytda, haqiqiy san'at asarlari bilan bog'liq mulohazalar, yangiliklar bilan nashr uchun xaridorgir kontent tayyorlash imkoniyati saqlanib qolmoqda. Masalan, muzey haqida material tayyorlayotgan jurnalist XVI asrga doir tasviriy san'at asari haqida yoki ko'hna milliy kuylarimiz haqida o'quvchi uchun yangilik bo'lgan, unutilgan jihatlarni bugun bilan uyg'unlashtirib maqola yozishi mumkin.

Shu o'rinda art-jurnalist faoliyati qaysi vazifalarni qamrab olishiga aniqlik kiritsak. Art-jurnalist san'at va madaniyatning turli yo'nalishlarida quyidagi funksiyalarni bajaradi:

- *Tahlil va tanqid qilish:* Art-jurnalistning asosiy vazifasi san'at asarlarini, jumladan, rasmlar, filmlar, spektakllar, musiqa va qo'shiqlarni tahlil qilish, ular haqida materiallari orqali o'z fikrini bildirishdir. U asarni tanqid qilishi, muallifning ijodiy uslubini baholashi, asar mazmuni mavzusini sharhlashi mumkin.

- *Intervyu olish:* jurnalist rassomlar, yozuvchilar, musiqachilar, rejissyorlar va boshqa san'at vakillari bilan suhbatlar o'tkazib, ularning yaratgan asarlari, ijodiy g'oyalari haqida fikrlarini olishi mumkin. Bunday intervyular mustaqil material sifatida e'lon qilinishi yoki muayyan asar sharhi, tahliliga bag'ishlangan publitsistik maqolaga kiritilishi mumkin.

- *Sharhlar va maqolalar tayyorlash:* Art-jurnalist san'at va madaniyatning turli sohalari borasida maqolalar, sharhlar, reportajlar, portret ocherklar, esse va boshqa ko'plab janrlarda materiallar yozadi. U madaniy tadbirlar, ko'rgazmalar, festivallar, taqdimotlarni yoritishi, shuningdek, san'at asarlariga tahliliy sharhlar, taqrizlar taqdim etishi mumkin.

- *Madaniy obyekt obrazini shakllantirish:* Art-jurnalist o'z taqrizlari va tahliliy materiallari bilan u yoki bu madaniy obyekt (rassom, ijodkor, kino) haqidagi jamoatchilik fikriga ta'sir o'tkazish imkoniyatiga ega. Bu orqali u o'quvchilarning ko'z o'ngida qahramoni portretiga chizgi berib, u haqidagi tasavvurni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

- *PR va media faoliyati:* Art-jurnalist ommaviy axborot vositalari orqali rassomlar, galereyalar va boshqa madaniy tashkilotlarning loyihalarini qo'llab quvvatlab, ularning faoliyatini targ'ib qilishi mumkin.

San'at jurnalisti yoritadigan san'at turi va o'zi ishlayotgan ommaviy axborot vositasining yo'nalishiga qarab, farq qilishi mumkin. Quyida ayrim ixtisosliklarni keltirib o'tamiz:

- *Tasviriy san'at*: rassomlik, haykaltaroshlik, chizmachilik, badiiy fotografiya va tasviriy san'atning boshqa turlariga ixtisoslashgan art-jurnalistlar. Ular san'at asarlarini tahlil qiladi, ko'rgazmalarni yoritadi, sharhlaydi, rassomlardan intervyu oladi va zamonaviy san'at yo'nalishlaridan xabardor qiladi.

- *Kino va teatr*: Kino va teatr san'atiga ixtisoslashgan jurnalistlar film va spektakllarga sharhlar, taqrizlar yozadi, rejissyor va aktyorlar bilan suhbatlar tayyorlaydi, davriy nashrlarga kino va teatr sohasidagi yangiliklar, muammolarga bag'ishlangan turli janrdagi materiallarni taqdim etadi.

- *Musiqqa va konsertlar*: Musiqqa va konsertlarga ixtisoslashgan art-jurnalist musiqiy albomlar va konsertlar haqida taqrizlar yozadi, xonandalar, bastakorlar va san'at arboblardan intervyu oladi, musiqqa olamidagi voqealar, tendensiyalarni yoritadi.

- *Zamonaviy madaniyat va yangi trendlar*: bu ixtisoslikda faoliyat olib boruvchi art-jurnalist moda, dizayn, arxitektura hamda zamonaviy madaniy hodisalarni sharhlashi va tahlil qilishi mumkin.

Ayrim manbalarda² adabiyot va kitoblarga bag'ishlangan mavzularni ham san'at jurnalistikasi yo'nalishiga kiritishadi. Ya'ni, adabiyot sohasidagi yangiliklar, badiiy asarlarga yozilgan taqriz va sharhlar, adabiyot vakillari bilan suhbatlar, yangi nashrlar taqdimotidan reportajlar ham art-jurnalistlar tomonidan tayyorlanadi. "Xitoy art-jurnalistikasi: genезis va rivojlanish tendensiyalari"³ mavzusida tadqiqot olib borgan filologiya fanlari nomzodi Chjao Yuanyuan ham o'z dissertatsiyasida Xitoyning

² О профессии арт-журналиста. – URL: <https://postupi.online/professiya/art-zhurnalist/> (мурожаат санаси 19.07.2024).

³ Чжао Юаньюань. Арт-журналистика китая: генезис и тенденции развития. Диссертация. Санкт-Петербург, 2021.

san'atga ixtisoslashgan bosma nashrlarini tasniflashda adabiy jurnallarni ham art-jurnalistikaning bir tarmog'i sifatida o'rganadi. Biroq, biz adabiyot yo'nalishini art-jurnalistika emas, balki yuqorida izohlaganimiz bir muncha kengroq soha – madaniy jurnalistika tarkibiga kiritishni joiz topdik.

Ko'chma ma'noda san'at leksemasini turli sohalarda yuksak mahorat bilan amalga oshirilgan ishlarga, kasblarga sifat berib, "san'at" yoki san'at darajasida deya qo'llaymiz. Masalan, rahbarlik san'ati, so'z san'ati, notiqlik san'ati, harbiy san'at, karving san'ati va hkz. Mana shu bosh va ko'chma ma'noda so'zning qo'llanilishi art-jurnalistika qamrab olishi mumkin bo'lgan san'at turlari, mavzular ko'lamida bahsli holatni yuzaga keltirishi mumkin. Dissertatsiyada ishning predmeti sifatida san'at turlarini chegaralab, uning asosan kino, teatr, tasviriy san'at, musiqa turlariga doir materiallar tahlili olindi.

Jurnalistikada ixtisoslashuv jarayonlariga qaytadigan bo'lsak, ayniqsa madaniy jurnalistikaga uning ta'siri sezilarli bo'ldi. Bu yo'nalishdagi kontent keng o'quvchi uchun mo'ljallangani va undan alohida madaniy tayyorgarlikni talab qilmasligi bilan ham ajralib turadi. Yuqoridagi ixtisoslashuvlar art-jurnalistikadagi eng asosiy yo'nalishlardir. Jurnalist o'z qiziqish doirasiga, maqsadli auditoriya ko'lamiga qarab, ulardan biri yoki bir nechtasini tanlashi mumkin.

O'zbek jurnalistikasida san'atning muayyan bir turiga ixtisoslashgan jurnalistlar ko'p emas. Art-jurnalistlar (Iqbol Qo'shshayeva, Gulchehra Umarova, Lobar Qobilova, Ilmira Rahmatullayeva, Zebo Mirzo, Gulmira Musajonova, Iroda Dadajonova, Charos Nizomiddinova, Nigora Umarova, Mapura Nabiyeva, Shahnoza Rofiyeva) faoliyatida musiqa, tasviriy san'at, kino, teatr, haykaltaroshlik, badiiy fotografiya, arxitektura, xalq amaliy san'ati kabi sohaning barcha yo'nalishlarida kontent tayyorlayotganini kuzatamiz. Ularning chiqishlari turli nashrlarda, san'atning turli sohalarida o'z aksini topadi. Buni ma'lum ma'noda art-jurnalistikada

universallashtirish deb atash mumkin. Binobarin, Rossiya⁴, Xitoy⁵, AQSH⁶, Daniya⁷ tajribasida nashrlar tor mutaxassislikdagi tarmoqlarga: teatr, musiqa, kino, tasviriy san'at, muzeylar jurnalistikasiga ixtisoslashgan. Milliy matbuotimizda esa, bugungi kunda asosan kino hamda teatr san'ati sohasiga ixtisoslashish nisbatan shakllangan. Mahliyo Mirsoatova, Shohida Eshonboboyeva, Shohira Hamro, Shohsanam Xidirova, Feruza Nodirova, Dilobar Asliddin qizi kabi art-jurnalistlar kino san'atining yutuq va kamchiliklariga doir mavzularni muntazam yoritayotgan bo'lsa, Shohruh Abdurasulov, Matluba Temur qizi, Shahribonu Imomova, Javlon Jovliyev kabi mualliflar jamoasi asosan teatr san'atining faoliyati, sahna asarlari tahlili, dramaturgiyadagi o'ziga xosliklar borasida jurnalistik materiallar tayyorlamoqda.

Xulosa

Sahna va ekran san'ati sintez san'at turlaridan sanaladi. Unda rassom, aktyor, rejissyor, bastakor, xonanda, dramaturg, operator, pardozi, libos ishlari uyg'unlikda yaxlit san'at asarining yaratilishiga xizmat qiladi. O'zida bir qancha san'at turlarini jamlagan kino va teatr san'ati hamisha katta auditoriya e'tiborida bo'lgan. Unda estetik zavq ulashish vazifasi bilan birga ijtimoiy qarashlar yig'indisi, siyosiy targ'ibot yuki ham birday ahamiyatli. O'zbek art-jurnalistikasida mazkur yo'nalishlarga qisman ixtisoslashuv shakllanganining sababi matbuot aynan shu omillarga: sahna va ekran san'atidagi ijtimoiy yukning targ'ibotiga keng urg'u berilganida ko'rinadi. Bunday yondashuv matbuotning ilk faoliyatida ham, bugungi zamonaviy ko'rinishlarida ham o'z aksini topgan.

⁴ Орлова Т.Д. Театральная журналистика. Теория и практика. В 2 ч./БГУ – Минск, 2001 – 2002. – Ч.1. – 146 с.; Ч. – 140 с.; Борзенко В.В. Российская театральная журналистика 1808 – 1991 г.; Курышева, Т. А. Музыкальная журналистика и музыкальная критика: уч. пособие для студентов вузов [Текст] / Т. А. Курышева. – М.: Владос-Пресс, 2007. – 296 с.

⁵ Чжао Юаньюань. Арт-журналистика Китая: генезис и тенденции развития. Диссертация. Санкт-Петербург, 2021.

⁶ Simone Varriale. Music, journalism, and the study of cultural change. – URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272621294_Music_journalism_and_the_study_of_cultural_change (мурожаат санаси 25.06.2024)

⁷ Susanne Janssen (1999). Art journalism and cultural change. The coverage of the arts in Dutch newspapers 1965-1990. Poetics 26 (1999) 329-348. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-422X\(99\)00012-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-422X(99)00012-1) (мурожаат санаси 22.02.2022.)

O'zbek matbuotida kino va teatr jurnalistikasiga ixtisoslashuv mazkur yo'nalishlarda alohida bosma nashrlar: "Teatr", "Kino", "Sinema magazin", "Kino san'ati" kabi jurnallar faoliyatining yo'lga qo'yilganida ham ko'rinadi. Garchi ularning hammasi ham bugungi kunga qadar yashab qolmagan bo'lsada, san'atning mazkur tarmoqlarida ixtisoslashgan jurnalistlar jamoasi shakllanishiga hissa qo'shdi.

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ISSUES OF SPECIALIZATION IN ART JOURNALISM

Zabarjad BOBOJONOVA

Abstract. *This article discusses specialization in journalism, in particular, the stages of formation of specialists who cover and analyze art and its types, art*

journalists, and the role of artists in this process. The activities of art journalists working in the field today are partially analyzed. It also clarifies what tasks the art journalistic activity covers and its functions are classified. The influence of periodicals dedicated to certain types of art on the development of specialized journalists in the field is studied.

Keywords: art journalist, criticism, culture, artistic taste, specialization.

TRAVEL JOURNALISM: THE ROLE OF ENGLISH AND ESSENTIAL VOCABULARY IN TOURISM STUDIES

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Abstract. *This article examines the field of travel journalism, focusing on the significance of English and specialized travel vocabulary in tourism studies. As English is the primary language of tourism and travel media, students studying tourism gain essential skills through English, which enables them to communicate effectively with a global audience. The study explores how English proficiency enhances the ability to describe destinations, connect with diverse readers, and convey unique travel experiences through nuanced vocabulary. Essential travel terms and language conventions used in travel journalism are analyzed, and the paper discusses how these linguistic tools empower tourism professionals to create captivating narratives that inspire global travel. By reviewing current practices in tourism studies, the article highlights how language proficiency, vocabulary mastery, and intercultural awareness equip tourism students to excel in travel journalism.*

Keywords: travel journalism, tourism studies, English in tourism, travel vocabulary, intercultural communication.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry thrives on storytelling, making travel journalism an influential component of global tourism. Through articles, blogs, and travel guides, travel journalists craft narratives that inspire readers to explore new destinations. In this context, English serves as the lingua franca, connecting readers, writers, and travelers from various cultures. Travel journalism uses precise language to evoke the atmosphere of places, articulate experiences, and convey cultural nuances, bridging the gap between destinations and potential travelers.

This article delves into the role of English and travel-specific vocabulary in tourism studies, highlighting how these elements contribute to effective travel journalism. For tourism students, mastering English language skills and specialized vocabulary is crucial, as it allows them to communicate effectively in a highly competitive, globalized industry. By learning to use descriptive terms, cultural references, and industry-specific jargon, students enhance their ability to capture the essence of destinations and connect with readers across diverse backgrounds. Through an exploration of vocabulary types, the role of English in tourism, and practical language tools, this article sheds light on the intersection of language proficiency and travel journalism.

English is the dominant language of the tourism industry, spoken by professionals and travelers alike. Its role in tourism studies, particularly in travel journalism, is essential due to its ability to reach a wide international audience. The globalization of tourism has cemented English as the universal language, and tourism students must develop English proficiency to succeed in careers that require effective cross-cultural communication (Crystal, 2003).

In travel journalism, English enables writers to produce content that appeals to a broad demographic. English is used in travel blogs, magazines, social media, and

guidebooks, allowing tourism professionals to create widely accessible narratives. According to the World Travel & Tourism Council (2020), English-language travel publications represent a large percentage of global travel media, underscoring the importance of mastering English for tourism students. English also facilitates collaboration with international tourism boards, media outlets, and readers from diverse backgrounds, helping travel journalists present an inclusive perspective on destinations.

English proficiency in travel journalism involves not only basic communication but also an understanding of advanced descriptive language, persuasive writing, and cultural sensitivity. Tourism students trained in English are better equipped to write articles that highlight cultural diversity, historical significance, and geographical uniqueness. This ability to convey intricate details makes English a valuable asset in creating authentic travel narratives, furthering students' careers in tourism media.

Vocabulary plays a vital role in travel journalism, where precision and vivid descriptions are key. For tourism students, learning specific travel vocabulary is integral to creating impactful narratives. Travel vocabulary can be categorized into several types:

Descriptive language: words and phrases that describe landscapes, architecture, and atmospheres, such as "breathtaking," "picturesque," and "serene." These terms help travel journalists paint a picture in the reader's mind.

Cultural vocabulary: terms that convey cultural aspects of a location, such as "heritage," "customs," and "festivals." Using culturally relevant language adds depth to travel writing and appeals to readers interested in the unique characteristics of destinations (Holland & Huggan, 2000).

Geographical terminology: words like "peninsula," "archipelago," "plateau," and "cove" are common in travel journalism. This terminology helps tourism students

provide clear descriptions of locations, enhancing the reader's understanding of the area's physical layout.

Tourism industry terms: words like "sustainability," "ecotourism," "hospitality," and "culinary tourism" are increasingly popular in travel journalism, as the focus shifts toward responsible travel and niche tourism markets.

Storytelling vocabulary: terms like "journey," "odyssey," "adventure," and "exploration" emphasize the experiential nature of travel. These words help convey a sense of excitement and discovery, which is central to engaging travel narratives (Bruner, 2005).

The mastery of these vocabularies is vital for tourism students who aim to excel in travel journalism. The ability to use precise, sensory language enables students to capture and convey the essence of a destination. Training in tourism studies often includes exercises that help students expand their vocabulary through descriptive writing and experiential learning projects, where they are encouraged to apply their vocabulary knowledge in real-world contexts.

Teaching travel vocabulary and descriptive language in tourism studies

Tourism studies programs incorporate travel vocabulary and descriptive language into the curriculum through specialized courses and hands-on projects. By integrating vocabulary-building exercises, educators enable students to develop the language needed to convey vibrant travel stories. Techniques for teaching travel vocabulary include:

Vocabulary expansion exercises: exercises that focus on synonyms and adjectives for common travel terms help students diversify their language. For instance, instead of using "beautiful," students are encouraged to use "stunning," "charming," or "idyllic" to capture nuances (Morgan & Pritchard, 1998).

Immersive learning: many tourism programs use immersive methods such as field trips or virtual tours, which allow students to practice descriptive language in

real settings. This experience-based learning helps students develop vocabulary in a context that mimics travel journalism.

Writing workshops: workshops in tourism programs focus on storytelling, guiding students to use engaging vocabulary and structure their narratives effectively. Through peer reviews and feedback, students learn to refine their language and produce polished travel articles (Holliday, Hyde, & Kullman, 2004).

By equipping students with essential travel vocabulary and descriptive writing skills, tourism programs prepare them to communicate effectively with a global audience. This focus on language helps students in tourism studies meet industry expectations and excel in careers that combine storytelling with cultural insights.

Travel journalism often involves describing and respecting the cultures of diverse destinations. Tourism students trained in intercultural communication learn to avoid stereotypes and present culturally accurate portrayals of people and places. English, as a globally recognized language, allows tourism professionals to reach a wide readership while promoting cultural understanding (Hannerz, 1996).

Courses in tourism studies emphasize sensitivity and accuracy in language, teaching students to balance informative content with respect for local traditions and values. By fostering intercultural competence, tourism programs ensure that future travel journalists produce content that resonates with international readers and promotes cultural appreciation.

CONCLUSION

The field of travel journalism is an essential part of the tourism industry, where English proficiency and a robust vocabulary enable professionals to create compelling narratives. Tourism students benefit from mastering descriptive language, cultural terminology, and industry-specific jargon, which allows them to communicate effectively in a globalized field. By learning to describe destinations

vividly, convey cultural nuances, and engage readers through storytelling, tourism students are better equipped for careers in travel media.

Through tourism studies programs, students gain exposure to vocabulary-building exercises, immersive learning experiences, and intercultural communication training, all of which are crucial for producing high-quality travel journalism. As the demand for culturally sensitive, insightful travel narratives continues to grow, the role of English and specialized vocabulary in tourism studies will remain vital. By honing these language skills, tourism students can contribute to the global exchange of ideas and perspectives that is central to the tourism industry.

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SAYOH JURNALISTIKASI: TURIZM O'QISHDA INGLIZ TILI VA ASOSIY SO'Z TO'G'RISINI O'RNI.

Aziza PIRMATOVA

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola sayyohlik jurnalistikasi sohasini ko'rib chiqadi va turizmni o'rganishda ingliz tili va ixtisoslashtirilgan sayohat lug'atining ahamiyatiga e'tibor qaratadi. Ingliz tili turizm va sayohat ommaviy axborot vositalarining asosiy tili bo'lganligi sababli, turizmni o'rganayotgan talabalar ingliz tili orqali muhim ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lishadi, bu ularga global auditoriya bilan samarali muloqot qilish imkonini beradi. Tadqiqot ingliz tilini bilish yo'nalishlarni tasvirlash, turli o'quvchilar bilan bog'lanish va noyob sayohat tajribasini nozik lug'at orqali etkazish qobiliyatini qanday oshirishini o'rganadi. Sayohat jurnalistikasida qo'llaniladigan asosiy sayohat atamaları va til konvensiyalari tahlil qilinadi va ushbu lingvistik vositalar turizm mutaxassislariga global sayohatlarni ilhomlantiradigan jozibali rivoyatlarni yaratishga qanday imkon berishini muhokama qiladi. Maqolada turizmni o'rganish bo'yicha joriy amaliyotlarni ko'rib chiqish orqali tilni bilish, so'z boyligini egallash va madaniyatlararo xabardorlik turistik talabalarni sayohat jurnalistikasi bo'yicha yuqori darajaga ko'tarishga qanday yordam berishiga urg'u beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: sayohat jurnalistikasi, turizmshunoslik, turizmda ingliz tili, sayohat lug'ati, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

TAQDIMOT TAYYORLASH SAN'ATI: ILM, IJOD VA AMALIY SAMARADORLIK

Gulnoza DJURAKULOVA Shavkatovna

*O'zbekiston Jurnalistika va ommaviy
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Annotatsiya: *Taqdimotni yaratish va uni tinglovchilarga yetkazish jarayoni nafaqat texnologiyaga, balki lingvistik va semiotik yondashuvlarga ham asoslanadi. Ushbu maqolada taqdimotni tayyorlash, uni samarali o'tkazish uchun lingvistik, psixologik va dizayn elementlarini uyg'unlashtirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Material filologik va pedagogik asoslarda yoritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: taqdimot, matn, fiologiya, semiotika, dizayn.

KIRISH

Hozirgi zamonda taqdimot nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki bilimlar, ishonchlar va innovatsiyalarni auditoriyaga samarali yetkazish vositasi hisoblanadi. Taqdimotlar ilmiy, amaliy yoki ijodiy maqsadlarga xizmat qiladi va ularning sifati tinglovchilarning qiziqishi, tushunishi va yodda saqlashiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi.

Taqdimotni yaratish va uni tinglovchilarga yetkazish jarayoni nafaqat texnologiyaga, balki lingvistik va semiotik yondashuvlarga ham asoslanadi. Ushbu maqolada taqdimotni tayyorlash, uni samarali o'tkazish uchun lingvistik, psixologik

va dizayn elementlarini uyg'unlashtirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Material filologik va pedagogik asoslarda yoritiladi.

Taqdimot va til: filologik yondashuv

Taqdimot muvaffaqiyati nafaqat vizual va texnik jihatlariga, balki nutqning lingvistik tozaligi va emotsional ta'siriga ham bog'liq. Filologiya nuqtai nazaridan qaraganda, samarali taqdimot quyidagi unsurlarni o'z ichiga olishi lozim:

1. Nutq tuzilishi va uslubi

Til tuzilmasining mantiqiyliги taqdimotning tushunarli bo'lishini ta'minlaydi.

Ushbu tamoyillar qo'llaniladi:

- Ravonlik: murakkab gaplar o'rniga sodda va qisqa gaplardan foydalanish.
- Tugallanganlik: har bir fikr aniq bayon qilinib, o'zaro bog'liq bo'lishi kerak.
- Matn va og'zaki nutq uyg'unligi: slayd matni va og'zaki bayon bir-birini takrorlamasligi, balki to'ldirishi kerak.

2. Leksik-semantik uyg'unlik

Olimlar Semichov (2009) va Rasulov (2015) lingvistikani ma'no yaratishda asosiy vosita deb ta'kidlashgan. Taqdimot matnida ortiqcha sinonimlardan foydalanish yoki professional jargonni haddan tashqari ishlatish auditoriya e'tiborini chalg'itadi. Shuning uchun taqdimot tili quyidagi talablarni qondirishi kerak:

- Auditoriyaning til darajasiga mos bo'lishi.
- Murakkab atamalarni tushuntirish bilan boyitish.
- Qisqa va samarali iboralar orqali asosiy ma'lumotni yetkazish.

3. Fonetik va ritmik jihatlar

Og'zaki nutqda fonetik va ritmik jihatlar tinglovchining e'tiborini ushlab turishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Taqdimot davomida ovoz balandligi, intonatsiya va pauzalar orqali tinglovchilarni jalb qilish mumkin. Shu bilan birga, tilning melodik

xususiyatlari, ayniqsa o'zbek tilidagi shoirona ta'sirchanlik, taqdimotda estetik ozuqa berishi mumkin.

Taqdimotni filologik jihatdan tayyorlash bosqichlari

1. Maqsad va auditoriyani aniqlash

Taqdimotdan oldin auditoriya tahlil qilinadi: ularning bilim darajasi, ehtiyojlari va tilga bo'lgan talablarini o'rganish zarur. Shuningdek, taqdimot maqsadi (bilim berish, qiziqish uyg'otish yoki motivatsiya berish) aniqlanishi kerak.

2. Tuzilmani ishlab chiqish

Filologik yondashuvda tuzilma ma'naviy va semantik uyg'unlikni ta'minlaydi.

Kirish qismi: auditoriyaga savol berish yoki qiziqarli hikoya orqali e'tibor tortish.

Asosiy qism: dalillar, faktlar va ma'lumotlar aniq mantiqiy ketma-ketlikda joylashtirilishi lozim.

Xulosa: olingan natijalarni umumlashtirish va auditoriyani harakatga undash.

3. Matn va slayd tayyorlash

Slayd matnlari sodda, qisqa va ma'no jihatidan aniq bo'lishi kerak. O'zbek tilida ishlatiladigan sinonimlar, metaforalar va iboralarning boyligi taqdimotga estetik go'zallik qo'shadi. Shu bilan birga, tarjima qilingan terminologiyani o'zbek tilining o'ziga xos qoidalariga moslashtirish muhimdir.

Lingvistik va semiotik elementlarning vizualizatsiyadagi o'rni

Taqdimotda til va tasvir uyg'unligi bilimlarni samarali yetkazishning asosiy tamoyillaridan biridir. Vizualizatsiya semiotik belgilar orqali axborotni soddalashtirish va eslab qolishni osonlashtiradi. Filologik jihatdan quyidagilar muhim:

Ramzlar va metaforalar: vizual elementlar lingvistik ma'no bilan boyitilishi kerak.

Muloqot semiotikasi: ranglar, shakllar va joylashuv ta'sirchanlikni oshiradi.

Amaliy tavsiyalar

1. Nutqni oldindan mashq qilish: filologik jihatdan to'g'ri talaffuz, grammatik aniqlik va oson idrok qilinadigan uslubni mashq qilish kerak.
2. Hikoya va misollardan foydalanish: o'zbek xalqining boy folkloridan olingan hikoyalar va maqollar taqdimotga milliy ruh bag'ishlaydi.
3. Til boyligini oshirish: o'zbek tilidagi sinonim va iboralardan ehtiyotkorlik bilan foydalanish, ularni mavzuga moslashtirish.

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THE ART OF PRESENTATION PREPARATION: SCIENCE, CREATIVITY AND PRACTICAL EFFECTIVENESS

Gulnoza DJURAKULOVA Shavkatovna

Abstract: *The process of creating a presentation and delivering it to the audience is based not only on technology, but also on linguistic and semiotic approaches. This article examines the preparation of a presentation, combining linguistic, psychological and design elements for its effective delivery. The material is covered on philological and pedagogical grounds.*

Key words: presentation, text, philology, semiotics, design.

ORIGIN OF THE NAME OF THE CAT IN JAPANESE

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Abstract. *This thesis is a profound study of the “Neko” in Japanese literature, distinct from its Chinese counterpart. We explore the historical relationship of these names, the evolution of this animal's presence, and its diverse roles in the Japanese context. Our study underscores the cultural significance of cats in Japan, revealing the deep-rooted values and attitudes of the Japanese people.*

Keywords: cat, dog, Neko, animal, Buddhism, culture

Introduction

Origin of the name “Neko (byo)” and “Neko (cat)” in Japanese

The words “Neko” and “neko (byo)” are not just labels for a feline creature in Japanese, they carry a significant historical weight. “Neko” is a Japanese word, while “neko (byo)” is a word derived from Chinese. The fact that cats, believed to have been brought from the continent in ancient times, have a name like “Neko” that is not of Chinese origin, suggests a deeper historical connection. This connection may have come from the continent before the Chinese characters were used, or as cats settled in

the Japanese archipelago and became familiar to the Japanese people, they were given a name different from the Chinese, the Japanese word “Neko.”

Methods

Cats appeared in historical documents from the Heian period [1]. There is no mention of cats in the Kojiki or Nihon Shoki, written in the Nara period. The existence of cats can be confirmed in the Nihon Ryōiki, Japan’s oldest collection of Buddhist tales [2]. It is said that cats were brought to Japan at the same time as Buddhism, on the ships of Japanese envoys to the Sui and Tang dynasties from the Nara period to the early Heian period. In China, cats were used as working animals to protect critical Buddhist scriptures and essential books from rats. Therefore, when Buddhism was introduced to Japan, cats were brought along with the scriptures and essential books. It is thought that the kanji character for the cat, “byo,” was also brought to Japan simultaneously. Cats were also expressed as “raccoon dogs.” In the Nihon Ryoiki, in the 30th chapter of the first volume, it is written, “I became a raccoon dog on the first day of the New Year... (Wa Shogatsu Ichinichi, na tanuki...)” [5, 6]. In the literature [9], a detailed explanation is given of an episode in which a deceased father turns into a cat and appears at his son’s house.

Results

The first year I died, I was hungry, and on July 7, I went to your house as a giant snake. When I tried to enter your house, you caught me with your stick and threw me away. The following year, on May 5, I went to your house as a small red dog, but I called other dogs and drove them away, so I could not get anything to eat and returned home angry. However, on January 1 this year, when I entered your house as a cat, I ate my fill of the meat and various other delicacies offered at the previous night's Tamamatsuri. Then, for the first time, I could quench my hunger that had lasted three years. (*Excerpt from “New Edition of the Complete Collection of Japanese Classical Literature”*)

Descussion

This episode is considered one of the oldest descriptions of cats in Japan.

The word “Neko” appears in documents from the Heian period. Karaneko may have come from China (618-907) as a cat introduced from the Tang dynasty [2, 3]. Karaneko was a scarce animal at the time. For example, in the 34th chapter of The Tale of Genji (written from around 1001 to 1021), Wakana no Ue, there is an episode in which Kashiwagi tries to steal the cat kept by Onna Sannomiya in order to get closer to her.

“I wish I could at least get that cat. I cannot tell her how I feel but can comfort her in my loneliness.” However, then he went crazy and wondered how he could steal the cat, and even that was difficult.

(Original quote from “Wakana no Shita” in ‘New Edition: Complete Collection of Japanese Classical Literature 20, The Tale of Genji’)

Moreover, the cat says, “The Chinese cat is tiny and cute...”

Because it was a very precious pet, it was kept tied up on a leash to prevent it from escaping, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Illustrated Tale of Genji, with two cats tied to a string (red frame).

Owned by the National Diet Library

Because the Chinese cat was a rare and precious animal, it was especially prized among aristocrats and high priests, and its mysterious powers and beauty were often discussed. Because of its mysterious and inaccessible nature, living deep within the mansions of aristocrats and the imperial family, it was sometimes thought that the Chinese cat would become a nekomata (a monster that turns into an old cat, often with a forked tail) as it grew older (Figure 2). It is also thought that this influenced the tastes of ordinary people towards cats in later generations. It is also thought that this may have led to words and phrases that have a demonic quality to “cats.”

Figure 2. “Nekomata” from Toriyama Sekien’s “Gazu Hyakki Yakou” (1776)

The cat’s tail is split into two.

The Heian period was a time of cat boom. Reference [10] introduces the cats depicted in the “Shigisan Engi Emaki” (created around 1150) and other cat booms of the time.

In the Heian period, cats seem to have made the sound “need” [7, 8]. The following is written in the 34th chapter of “The Tale of Genji,” “Wakana no Ue” (Figure 3):

“Come and meow, “need,” so I stroked it and thought, “Maybe I should sleep too,” with a smile. (Modern Japanese translation: The cat came and meowed very cutely, “need,” so I stroked it and thought, “You’re being very proactive in wanting to sleep with me,” with a wry smile.)

Figure 3. “Genji Monogatari Ebyobu” Wakana-no-ue, part, National Institute of Japanese Literature

There is a theory that the name “Neko” (cat) comes from the sound of the cat's cry, “need” [7]. It is said that the name was created by adding the suffix “ko” (cute) to the sound of the cat’s cry. It is the same logic as calling a cute chicken that cries “hiyohiyo” a “hiyoko.” However, looking for the origin of “neko” in the Tale of Genji is a bit of a stretch. The “Honsho Wamyō,” compiled in 918, describes “Nekoma = Nekoma,” a small animal that catches mice and has a tiger-like appearance like a raccoon dog, and the “Wamyō Ruijusho,” a dictionary from 931 to 938, states that “Nekoma = Nekoman,” and there is a theory that ‘Neko’ was an

abbreviation of the old name “nekoma.” The term “cat” was probably established around 1001-1021 when The Tale of Genji was written. It seems natural to think that the term “cat” (neko) or “nekoma” (neko means to sleep) was associated with “neu neu” (to sleep). The question remains about where “cat” or “nekoma” came from, but it seems complicated to confirm this with literature.

During the Sengoku period (1467-1615), snakeskin sanshin instruments began to spread in what is now Okinawa, the Ryukyu Kingdom, and cat skin, which is larger and more accessible than snakeskin, began to be used. As a result, cat hunters began to appear in the city. For this reason, the custom of keeping cats indoors was established during this period.

Later in the Edo period, cats were allowed to live in the streets [1] (Figure 4), and wild cats were rarely seen, so “cat” came to be called “neko” and “karaneko” became obsolete. Today, “cat” is called “neko” (Neko: kun reading, byo: on reading). However, byo is never used alone to refer to a cat. It is used in compound words like “cat lover (Libya-ka).”

Figure 4. Utagawa Kuniyoshi’s “Cat Keeping Mice Away” is a 19th-century painting. The cat has a bell around its neck. Cats were only allowed to roam free like this in later times; during the Heian period, cats were tied up with strings to prevent them from escaping.

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YAPON TILIDA MUSHUK NOMINING KELIB KELISHI

Rina KOIKE

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezis yapon adabiyotidagi "Neko"ni xitoylik tadqiqotchilardan farqli ravishda chuqur o'rganishdir. Biz ushbu nomlarning tarixiy munosabatini, bu hayvonning mavjudligi evolyutsiyasini va uning yapon kontekstidagi turli rollarini o'rganamiz. Bizning tadqiqotimiz Yaponiyadagi mushuklarning madaniy ahamiyatini ta'kidlab, yapon xalqining chuqur ildiz otgan qadriyatlarini va munosabatlarini ochib beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: mushuk, it, Neko, hayvon, buddizm, madaniyat

THE HISTORY OF CATS IN JAPAN, THE ORIGIN OF “NEKO”

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Abstrakt. *This thesis is devoted to the “Neko” wild cat mentioned in Japanese literature and its pictorial expressions, the history of this animal’s appearance, and forms of use in the context of Japan. The research raised issues not mentioned before, thereby analyzing the subject area of Japanese literature.*

Keywords: *cat, Neko, animal, Japanese literature, culture*

Intraduction.

The arrival and settlement of cats and the “Neko” that appears in literature

Recent groundbreaking research has unveiled that the ancestors of the domestic cats and house cats that grace modern Japan arrived in Kyushu during the Heian period, then proliferated during the Kamakura period, and spread further north across the Japanese archipelago. This crucial information, derived by extracting and analyzing genetic information from the blood of modern cats, is a testament to the power of scientific investigation and has significantly enriched our understanding of the historical relationship between cats and Japanese culture [1-9].

Figure 1. Bone of an animal believed to be a cat from the Yayoi period around the 2nd century BC, unearthed at the Karakami ruins in Iki City, Nagasaki Prefecture, during an excavation survey conducted by Iki City in 2011.

While the bone unearthed at the Karakami ruins in Iki City, Nagasaki Prefecture, during an excavation survey conducted by Iki City in 2011 is believed to be that of a cat from the Yayoi period around the 2nd century BC, no species identification has been performed using genetic or amino acid analysis. Therefore, doubts remain whether it can be conclusively determined to be a “cat” bone.

Methods.

Although it has become clear that the genetic traces of “cats” date back to the Heian period, it seems that animals familiar to Japanese people as “Neko,” “nekoma,” or “tanuki (raccoon dog)” existed in the Japanese archipelago even earlier. Prior to genetic research, several archaeological arguments have been presented. Cat bones from the Yayoi period around the 2nd century BC were excavated from the Karakami ruins in Iki City, Nagasaki Prefecture [4, 5]. However, since the morphological

differences between cats and wildcats, especially in young animals, are minor, making it difficult to distinguish between the two, and no species identification has been performed using genetic or amino acid analysis, doubts remain as to whether the bones are those of “cats” [6]. Sueki (earthenware) with cat paw prints was discovered in the Mino Kofun (6th-7th century) in Himeji City, Hyogo Prefecture [7]. It has been reported that small animal footprints believed to be from a cat were found on a piece of sueki pottery from the late Kofun period (late 6th to early 7th century) found in a moat surrounding a burial mound near the ruins of the Koudo-ji Temple, a national historic site in Mihama-cho, Fukui Prefecture [8]. However, there are some difficulties in assuming that these bones and footprints are the direct ancestors of the domestic cats (domestic cats) living in modern Japan. The Iriomote wildcat and the Tsushima wildcat lived in the Stone Age before the establishment of Japanese civilization. They are thought to have migrated from the continent to the Japanese archipelago, connected to the mainland during the glacial period 100,000 to 200,000 years ago. The Iriomote wildcat and the Tsushima wildcat are members of the *Bengalensis* genus, which branched off from the *Bengalensis* cat and are genetically different from the domestic cat, which belongs to the *Felis* genus. They do not mate with each other in the natural environment [9]. DNA testing is required to distinguish them.

Figure 2. Sue ware with cat paw prints excavated from the Mino Kofun (6th to 7th century) in Himeji City, Hyogo Prefecture.

From the Asuka to the Nara period, animals resembling cats were collectively called 'raccoon dogs (Nekomata). Among them were “neko,” related to modern wildcats, and unlike today, they lived in large numbers within human habitats. It is not scientifically known whether there was a species that was related to modern housecats. Cats appeared in historical documents from the Heian period, such as “Konjaku Monogatari” (compiled after the 1120s), a significant historical document. In 'Okura no Daibu Fujiwara no Kiyokado, Neko wo Osoreru Koto' (Okura no Daibu Fujiwara no Kiyokado, Neko wo Osoreru Koto), there is a story about a man who hated cats [15]. It is assumed that “neko” were already common animals at the time of this story. However, it has yet to be confirmed that these were domestic or house cats (ieneko) living in modern Japan. The theory that cats related to modern house cats (Renko) came from the continent during the Heian or Nara period is consistent with the results of genetic analysis [2, 3]. However, it is also certain that raccoon dogs (nekomas) inhabited the Japanese archipelago and lived in cities before that.

The following description is from Sakujin Kirino and Yutaka Yoshikado's “The History of Cats in Japan” [16].

Results.

Fujiwara no Sukekimi, who appears in 'Okura no Daifu Fujiwara no Kiyotaka, Kowa Nekogo' in the “Konjaku Monogatari,” is known for collecting taxes in a truly unique way. Fujiwara no Kiyotaka tried to avoid paying the government taxes he should have paid. His weakness was well-known on the streets. He was 'afraid of cats.' People would bring out cats in front of him and tease him. Fujiwara no Sukekimi was clever. Fujiwara no Sukekimi was clever. He invented a 'cat torture' that would bring some people joy by having Kiyokaze surrounded by five cats and dogs in a small room. While seemingly humorous, this story reflects the unique relationship between cats and humans in Japanese history. Kiyokaze surrendered and delivered all the official goods at once.

“Cat-Fearing Tayu” was regularly toyed with in cat pranks. Cats were just around the city. The cats used for “cat torture” were said to be “grey-spotted” cats, “over one foot tall,” with “eyes as red as amber.” The original cat breed was an agouti, with “stripes on each hair,” a full blackish-brown color (whole-body pattern), and a wildcat type. The ‘grey spots’ were that. These “cat pranks” were playful acts and reflected the cultural perception of cats in Japanese society, particularly in the Heian period.

During the Heian period, it is possible that “cats” that would be classified as “wildcats” today lived in the city.

Descution

On the other hand, the word "Chinese cat" appears in documents from the Heian period. It is thought that the name Karaneko may have come from the Tang dynasty (618-907, China) [11, 12]. Moreover, Karaneko was a scarce animal at the time. For example, in the 34th chapter of *The Tale of Genji* (written around 1001 and completed around 1021), Wakana no Ue says, “Kaneko no Ito Chiisaku o Kashige Naru wo (Karaneko is very small and cute...)”. Until the Middle Ages, cats were precious animals, and it was expected to keep them tied to a string, as shown in *Figura 3*. As a result, there was no opportunity for them to breed, and the number of cats stayed relatively high. In the 14th century, a picture scroll called *Ishiyama-dera Engi Emaki* (*Ishiyama-dera Engi Emaki*) depicts a cat tied to a merchant's house. It is assumed that the house was wealthy enough to keep a cat. Also, as shown in *Figure 4*, a woman from the ancient period, painted by Suzuki Harunobu, an ukiyo-e artist of the Edo period, comforts a cat tied to a string.

Figure 3. “Ishiyama-dera Engi Emaki” (Produced between 1324 and 1805)

A cat on a leash in the home of a wealthy merchant.

Figure 4. Suzuki Harunobu (1725? -70), Collection of the Boston Museum of Fine Arts

Ancient woman and a cat on a leash

It is said that the number of cats began to increase during the Sengoku to Edo periods [13]. As the era progressed, the population of Kyoto increased, and rat damage became more serious. In 1602, the Kyoto Shoshidai (the shogunate's administrative agency established in Kyoto) issued the “Cats at Large” by Tokugawa Ieyasu and had cats patrol the streets to catch rats. This was recorded in the diary of Nishinotoin Tokiyoshi (1589-1639 AD). A notice prohibiting keeping cats tied up or buying and selling cats was posted at Ichijo-no-Tsuji in Kyoto and spread nationwide. This marked a significant turning point in the history of Japanese cats [14]. From then on, cats were allowed to live freely in the city. Unlike when they were tied up and kept indoors, cats were now free to breed, increasing their numbers. In the flourishing Edo culture, cats were featured in various cultural works by people of all classes, from the upper class to the ordinary people, ushering in an age of prosperity. As shown in Figure 5, many cats were depicted in ukiyo-e prints.

Figure 5. Utagawa Kuniyoshi (1798-1861) from “Sono mama Higuchi: 53 cat-keeping stories.”

Cats drawn in the Edo period are characterized by their short tails, as seen in Figure 5, and their tails are often bent in the middle. In contrast to the cats drawn before the Edo period, most of which have long, gently curving tails, one cannot help but feel something unusual about them. One theory is that the cause lies in the relationship between Chinese cats (neko) and cat demons (nekomata). Chinese cats and nekomata have an exciting relationship in Japanese folklore and yokai legends. This relationship between the two has influenced the tastes towards cats of ordinary people since the Edo period and even the distribution of cat species living in modern Japan.

Chinese cats were precious creatures from China and lived in the depths of the aristocrats' mansions and members of the imperial family, where they were adored. For this reason, their mysterious nature and unique abilities have often been spoken of. In the Kamakura period *Kokin Chomonshu* (1254, Tachibana Shigeki), there is a story about a Chinese cat kept at a mountain villa in Saga that ran away holding a treasured sword for protection, and it is said that this cat had transformed into a demon.

Nekomata, a cat-like monster, is a yokai in folklore and ghost stories from all over Japan. It is said to be an old cat that transforms into a monster (Figure 6). The oldest mention of nekomata is in *Meigetsuki* (1180–1235), a diary written by Fujiwara Teika, a nobleman of the Kamakura period. In an entry for August 2, 1233 (the first year of Tenpuku), there is a description of a “nekomata” that killed and ate several people in Nara in one night. Also, in *Tsurezuregusa* (Yoshida Kenko, 1330–1331), there is a description of a “nekomata” in Volume 226. This section introduces the story of a monster called “Nekomata” that lives deep in the mountains and eats people.

Figure 6. “Cat-mata” by Edo period artist Sawaki Takayuki (1707-72), from “Hyakkai Zukan” (Illustrated Scroll of One Hundred Monsters)

There are two main types of nekomata. One is a nekomata living in the mountains, and the other is a cat kept in a human home that grows old and transforms. The connection between karaneke and nekomata is especially seen in the latter type. As karaneke live a long life and grow old, their mystical powers increase, and they transform into nekomata. In the Edo period, the belief that a cat kept for a long time would become a nekomata as it grew older became common, and a custom of avoiding keeping cats for a long time was born. In this way, karaneke’s mysticism profoundly influences nekomata folklore, and the two are closely related to Japanese yokai culture. This even influences the distribution of cat types in modern books. In modern Japan, many cats with tails are bent in the middle, known as “tail-bending cats” or “hook-tailed cats.” [17] There are so many “tail-bending cats” in Japan due to several historical and genetic factors. During the Edo period, Dejima in Nagasaki

was a trading base with the Netherlands. Dutch trading ships brought cats with bent tails from Indonesia to exterminate rats. It is said that these cats landed in Nagasaki and bred there. The characteristic of bent-tail cats is genetic, and a gene called HES7 (Hairy and Enhancer of Split 7) is involved. HES7 is a gene that plays a vital role in forming somites. If this gene is mutated, the tail vertebrae decrease, the tail becomes shorter, the tail vertebrae are deformed, and the tail becomes bent [17] (*Figure 7*).

During the Edo period, it was believed that long-tailed cats, including Chinese cats, would split their tails into two over time and become the yōkai “nekomata,” so “bent tail cats” were favored because they would not be able to transform if their tails were bent from the beginning. In addition, bent-tail cats were said to “bring good luck” and were treasured as talismans for prosperous business. It is believed that the combination of these factors led to the widespread appearance of bent-tail cats in Japan. Many people love bent-tail cats because of their unique appearance and historical background.

Figure 7. X-ray image of the tail of a “curved cat.”

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YAPONIYADA MUSHUKLAR TARIXI: “NEKO”NING KELIB CHIQISHI

Rina KOIKE

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis yapon adabiyotida tilga olingan “Neko” yovvoyi mushuki va uning tasviriy ifodalari, ushbu hayvonning paydo bo‘lish tarixi va Yaponiya kontekstida foydalanish shakllariga bag‘ishlangan. Tadqiqot ilgari tilga olinmagan masalalarni ko‘tardi va shu bilan yapon adabiyotining mavzu sohasini tahlil qildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: mushuk, Neko, hayvon, yapon adabiyoti, madaniyati

**OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA TIL VA USLUB MASALASI:
TAHLIL, TASNIF, QIYOS
2024.11.30**

V Sho'ba: San'at va sayohat jurnalistikasi

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